

Global cold-chain related SARS-CoV-2 transmission

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29 **Abstract**

30 The COVID-19 pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2 poses a tremendous threat to
31 human society. SARS-CoV-2 is airborne and mainly transmitted through social
32 contact; however, it is highly debated whether cold-chain related transmission has
33 occurred. Here, we present a new method and distinguish two transmission routes by
34 detecting a lineage-specific reduction of SARS-CoV-2 evolutionary rate. After
35 analyzing 1,610,125 SARS-CoV-2 genomic sequences, we found that two outbreaks
36 in Xinfadi-Beijing and Auckland may be cold-chain related and respectively caused
37 by two mutation-dormant variants. A Dalian outbreak in July 2020 and a Yingkou
38 outbreak ten months later were epidemiologically connected and derived from a
39 cold-chain related variant. Mutation-dormant variants were detected during the spread
40 of spike D614G variant and the Delta Variant of Concern. Moreover, the earliest
41 SARS-CoV-2 variant (i.e., the most recent common ancestor of SARS-CoV-2) was
42 found to be a mutation-dormant variant. Its repeated spillover events were observed
43 during the last two years, indicating that the COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan could be
44 associated with spillover events from cold-chains. In all the observed cases, the virus
45 re-started mutating after the spillover events from cold-chains. A systematic
46 identification of spillover events revealed that the frequency of cold-chain related
47 transmission is in the order of magnitude of 0.1-10%. Our results indicate that that
48 cold-chain related transmission should be rare but may have happened globally.

49

50 **Keywords**

51 Cold-chain related transmission; SARS-CoV-2; COVID-19; D614G; Delta VOC;
52 Wuhan outbreak

53 **INTRODUCTION**

54 SARS-CoV-2, also known as 2019-nCoV, is a novel coronavirus first reported in the
55 end of 2019 [1-3]. It causes the coronavirus disease 19 (COVID-19) and has infected
56 more than 464 million people. It has been well-recognized that SARS-CoV-2 is
57 airborne and mainly transmitted through social contact. Infectious respiratory droplets
58 and aerosol particles can be released when infected people are speaking, coughing or
59 sneezing [4, 5]. Infectious virus can be recovered from smooth surfaces even after a
60 2-day incubation at room temperature [6]. SARS-CoV-2 can then be transmitted by
61 exposure to those infectious droplets and aerosol particles in air or on surfaces. If
62 transmission occurs through surfaces, it is indirect contact transmission. However,
63 after two years of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is still highly debated whether
64 cold-chain related SARS-CoV-2 transmission has occurred [7-13].

65
66 Cold-chain related SARS-CoV-2 transmission could be possible because the virus can
67 remain alive but inactive under a low temperature, suitable humidity surface [14].
68 When the virus is kept at 4°C for 14 days, its infectivity has little reduction [6].
69 However, many key factors have to be satisfied to allow cold-chain related
70 SARS-CoV-2 transmission, such as the viral load on contaminated surface, the
71 contaminated area, the environmental condition during the transportation, and the
72 amount of virus to which a person is exposed. These factors are highly variable, and it
73 is impossible to test these factors by using population cohort since it is not ethical.
74 Thus a novel approach is needed to analyze real world examples and examine whether
75 cold-chain related SARS-CoV-2 transmission has occurred.

76
77 A large number of viral genomic sequences and their epidemiologically associated
78 meta-data are available [15-19], and it may contain essential information about how
79 the virus was transmitted. When SARS-CoV-2 is transmitted through social contact,
80 the virus duplicates in human hosts with certain error rate (*i.e.*, mutation rate). In this
81 process, mutations are inevitable if the considered duration of time is long (Figure
82 1A). On the contrary, the virus does not duplicate and mutate under the cold-chain
83 related condition. If the considered duration of time is long, two routes of
84 transmission can be distinguished by detecting whether SARS-CoV-2 evolves
85 significantly slowly in the lineage (Figure 1A). Moreover, spillover clades can be

86 found, in which the virus re-starts mutating. Therefore, the analysis of lineage-specific
87 change in viral evolutionary rate may shed light on whether cold-chain related
88 SARS-CoV-2 transmission has occurred. In this study, we used the Coronavirus
89 GenBrowser (CGB) [20] to examine the available molecular epidemiological
90 evidence. Viral sequences were considered only if those sequences were isolated from
91 infected patients. Thus, those sequences were the results of viral transmission and
92 evolution in the real world. After analyzing 1,610,125 SARS-CoV-2 high-quality
93 genomic sequences and their epidemiologically associated meta-data, we provided a
94 panoramic vision of cold-chain related SARS-CoV-2 transmission and found that
95 cold-chain related transmission is rare, but it may have occurred globally.

96

97 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

98 **Coronavirus GenBrowser**

99 The data used in this study was obtained from the Coronavirus GenBrowser (CGB)
100 [20] that offers a panoramic vision of the transmission and evolution of SARS-CoV-2.
101 The CGB data file is “data.2021-09-02” that can be downloaded freely from
102 <https://ngdc.cncb.ac.cn/ncov/apis/archives/>. The data file, the size of which is 21.8
103 MB, was obtained by analyzing 1,610,125 SARS-CoV-2 high-quality genomic
104 sequences. It contains the tip-dated tree, the pre-analyzed genomic mutations, and
105 epidemiologically associated meta-data. Moreover, the latest CGB data set
106 (data.2022-02-10, $n = 3,186,359$ genomic sequences) was used to confirm one of
107 our conclusions.

108

109 **The probability that two dock workers were infected with the strain^{MRCA} in** 110 **Qingdao outbreak**

111 It has been documented that, to unload frozen cod, 71 dock workers were divided into
112 three groups, and each group worked for 10 hours between September 18 and 20,
113 2020 [21]. One group handled the frozen cod between 20:00 on September 19 and
114 06:00 on the next day. Two dock workers in this group were tested positive on
115 September 24 while others were negative. Therefore, the duration of the infection is
116 likely to be no more than 5 days.

117

118 The genome-wide evolutionary rate of SARS-CoV-2 is estimated as $\mu = 9.69 \times$
119 10^{-4} per nucleotide per year [20], or 7.88×10^{-2} per genome per day. It indicates
120 that a mutation occurs in a strain every 12.7 days. With the Poisson probability, we
121 can calculate the probability that more mutations accumulate in a short period of time
122 [20, 22]. It is

$$123 \quad P(x \geq \xi_{obs}) = 1 - \sum_{x=0}^{\xi_{obs}-1} e^{-\xi_{exp}} \xi_{exp}^x / x!,$$

124 where ξ_{obs} is the observed number of mutations ($\xi_{obs} \geq 1$), $\xi_{exp} = l\mu$, l the
125 duration of the infection, and μ the evolutionary rate per genome per day.

126

127 Under the null hypothesis, we assume that both dock workers were infected with the
128 strain^{MRCA} (Figure 2A), the probability of two or more mutations can be accumulated
129 in worker 1 within 5 days is 0.06, and the probability of one or more mutations can be
130 accumulated in worker 2 within 5 days is 0.32. By doubling the product of the
131 probability of the two events, the probability that two dock workers were infected
132 with the strain^{MRCA} can be obtained. The null hypothesis also indicates that the live
133 SARS-CoV-2 particle (with the mutation C1282T, or the blue one in Figure 2A)
134 isolated from surface swab samples of frozen cod outer package [21] should be due to
135 spot contamination of worker 1.

136

137 The alternative hypothesis is that two dock workers were infected with different
138 strains. Worker 1 was infected with the strain with the mutation C1282T, and worker 2
139 was infected with the strain^{MRCA} (Figure 2A).

140

141 **CGB Lineage Tracing**

142 The CGB [20] lineage tracing was used to analyze the strains isolated from
143 environment (*i.e.*, outer packages). The query sequences were aligned with the
144 reference genome (NC_045512) [2]. The aligned sequences were used as the input for
145 lineage tracing, and the closest nodes to each query sequence (measured as the

146 similarity of two genomic sequences) were identified on the tree.

147

148 **Identification of mutation-dormant variants**

149 To search for mutation-dormant variants in the SARS-CoV-2 evolutionary tree, we
150 started from the root and traversed the tree. For each node, we recorded its direct and
151 indirect non-mutated descendants. Considering a mutation-dormant variant, its
152 repetitive cold-chain related transmissions may cause a long non-mutated path
153 (LNMP) in the tip-dated evolutionary tree. In this study, we used the following
154 criteria to identify mutation-dormant variants. First, it was required that there are at
155 least two non-mutated strains with no ambiguous nucleotides. Second, the minimum
156 difference in collection date between the earliest and the latest non-mutated strains
157 should be greater than 100 days. Third, the LNMP should not depend on the existence
158 of a single non-mutated strain. In another word, if one of non-mutated strains is
159 removed, the LNMP should remain to be detectable. Forth, each side of the LNMP
160 should not rely on non-mutated strains submitted by a single organization. In this
161 study, we required that, if the longest branch in the LNMP is larger than 30 days,
162 strains on each side of the longest branch should be collected by two or more
163 submitting organizations. After applying those requirements, the mutation-dormant
164 variants were identified.

165

166 **Detection of significantly reduced evolutionary rate in a lineage**

167 The genome-wide evolutionary rate of SARS-CoV-2 was estimated as $\mu = 9.69 \times$
168 10^{-4} per nucleotide per year [20], or 7.88×10^{-2} per genome per day. It indicates
169 that a mutation occurs in a strain every 12.7 days. With the Poisson probability, we
170 can determine whether the evolutionary rate is significantly reduced [20, 22]. It is

$$171 P(x \leq \xi_{obs}) = \sum_{x=0}^{\xi_{obs}} e^{-\xi_{exp}} \xi_{exp}^x / x!,$$

172 where ξ_{obs} is the observed number of mutations on the branches, $\xi_{exp} = l\mu$, l the
173 summation length of branches related to the mutation-dormant variants, and μ the
174 evolutionary rate per genome per day. The test is one-tailed. Since it is a

175 lineage-specific test, it is independent on the demography of SARS-CoV-2.

176

177 Let us consider an example shown in Figure S7. We test whether evolutionary rate is
178 reduced between the node A and strain 5. In this case, we have $\xi_{obs} = 2$, and l is the
179 duration of time between the node A and strain 5.

180

181 The test can be easily extended to consider evolutionary rate heterogeneity. When
182 different genes evolve with different rates, P -value can be calculated using $\prod_i P(x \leq$
183 $\xi_{obs,i})$, where $\xi_{obs,i}$ is the the observed number of mutations on the i -th gene. The
184 evolutionary rate for each gene is given in Table S1.

185

186 **Multiple tests**

187 The test was generally performed to detect a mutation-dormant variant in a clade
188 (Figure S7). Since each strain should be examined, the number of strains in the clade
189 is the number of tests performed. Thus, if the clade has n strains, the Bonferroni
190 corrections [23] was performed to adjust the threshold for multiple tests (the desired
191 overall Type I error rate, *i.e.* the family-wise error rate, is 0.05). The threshold of
192 P -values is $0.05/n$.

193

194 Let us consider the example shown in Figure S7 and take the clade A. There are seven
195 strains in the clade, and seven tests are performed. The minimum P -value is observed
196 on the strain 1 because there are only two strains (strain 1 and 3) lacking mutations
197 since the clade emerges, and the strain 3 is collected earlier than the strain 1. If the
198 minimum P -value is less than the adjusted threshold for multiple tests, the
199 mutation-dormant variant is found. Since those strains share one evolutionary tree,
200 tests among different strains are not independent, which makes us conservative to
201 apply the Bonferroni correction.

202

203 **Evolutionary tree of a mutation-dormant variant**

204 To obtain the evolutionary tree of a mutation-dormant variant, each node from the
205 rooted CGB evolutionary tree ($n = 1,610,125$) was compared with the
206 mutation-dormant variant. All the nodes with genetic differences were filtered out.
207 Then the evolutionary tree for the mutation-dormant variant was obtained and was a
208 rooted tree (Figures 3, 4, 5 and 6). An example is provided as Supplementary movie to
209 show how to obtain the evolutionary tree by using the CGB.

210

211 **The distribution of evolutionary rate among SARS-CoV-2 strains**

212 To obtain the observed distribution of evolutionary rate among SARS-CoV-2 strains,
213 the evolutionary rate was calculated for each strain. It is the number of mutations in
214 each strain divided by its lineage length, measured as the number of days between the
215 collection date and the time of the most recent common ancestor (MRCA) of the
216 analyzed strains. The length of considered genomic sequences was considered in the
217 calculation. In total, 1,610,125 SARS-CoV-2 genomic sequences were analyzed.

218

219 To obtain the simulated distribution of evolutionary rate among SARS-CoV-2 strains
220 when there was no cold-chain related transmission, the annotated tip-dated tree was
221 obtained from the CGB ($n = 1,610,125$) [20]. To randomly assign mutations for each
222 branch, the Poisson probability was applied. That is

$$P(X = k_i) = e^{-\xi_{exp,i}} \xi_{exp,i}^{k_i} / k_i!$$

223 where k_i is the simulated number of mutations on the i -th branch, $\xi_{exp,i} = l_i \mu$, l_i
224 the length of the i -th branch, and μ the evolutionary rate per genome per day. The
225 genome-wide evolutionary rate was 9.69×10^{-4} per site per year, or 7.88×10^{-2}
226 per genome per day in this study, unless mentioned otherwise. There are 2,236,398
227 branches in the CGB evolutionary tree. Finally, the simulated number of mutations in
228 each strain was calculated, and the distribution of evolutionary rate was obtained from
229 the simulated data, in which there was no cold-chain related transmission.

230

231 **RESULTS**

232 **Evolutionary rate of SARS-CoV-2**

233 In total, 1,610,125 SARS-CoV-2 genomic sequences and their associated meta-data
234 were analyzed using the CGB [20]. All considered SARS-CoV-2 strains were isolated
235 from humans, thus those sequences represent the outcomes of viral transmission. The
236 genome-wide evolutionary rate was 9.69×10^{-4} per site per year (95% confidence
237 interval: $7.27 \times 10^{-4} - 1.23 \times 10^{-3}$), or 7.88×10^{-2} per genome per day. The
238 estimate is similar with other studies [24-27] but was obtained with a much larger
239 sample size.

240

241 The different evolutionary rates were obtained for different genes (Table S1). The
242 highest evolutionary rate was observed in noncoding regions (6.07×10^{-3} per site
243 per year), and the lowest evolutionary rate in the E gene (1.62×10^{-5} per site per
244 year). There was two orders of magnitude difference in evolutionary rate, thus
245 evolutionary rate heterogeneity was expected.

246

247 **The probability of a mutation-dormant variant**

248 When SARS-CoV-2 is transmitted through social contact, the virus duplicates in
249 human hosts with certain error rate (*i.e.*, mutation rate). In this process, mutations are
250 inevitable if the considered duration of time is long. Therefore, under the null
251 hypothesis assuming that SARS-CoV-2 is transmitted through social contact, the virus
252 mutates and the probability that SARS-CoV-2 does not mutate within 100 days in one
253 lineage is very small ($P = 3.76 \times 10^{-4}$). The conclusion holds even using the lower
254 bound of confidence interval of estimated evolutionary rate ($P = 2.70 \times 10^{-3}$). The
255 test is lineage-specific, which means that a specific lineage is considered instead of
256 the whole viral population.

257

258 Since different regions of SARS-CoV-2 may have different evolutionary rates [20],
259 we examined whether evolutionary rate heterogeneity affects the calculation of the
260 *P*-value. Let us consider two viral genes A and B. Given the duration of time *t*, the

261 probability that the virus does not mutate in one lineage is $e^{-t\mu_A}$ and $e^{-t\mu_B}$, where
262 μ_A and μ_B is the evolutionary rate for gene A and B. The probability that the virus
263 does not mutate in both genes is the product of the two probabilities, $e^{-t\mu_A} \cdot e^{-t\mu_B} =$
264 $e^{-t(\mu_A+\mu_B)} = e^{-t\mu_{A+B}}$, indicating that the evolutionary rate of two or multiple genes
265 can be combined. Therefore, evolutionary rate heterogeneity does not affect the
266 calculation of the P -value when no mutations occur in the lineage.

267

268 If mutations occur, evolutionary rate heterogeneity may have an effect on the
269 calculation of the P -value. In this case, evolutionary rate heterogeneity can be
270 considered by taking different evolutionary rates for different genes (see Methods).

271

272 **Expected unimodal and observed bimodal distribution of evolutionary rate**

273 The virus re-starts mutating after the spillover events from cold-chains (Figure 1A)
274 and these repeated spillover events from cold-chains could affect the distribution of
275 evolutionary rate in the sample. When there is no cold-chain related transmission, the
276 simulated distribution of evolutionary rate is unimodal. However, the observed
277 distribution of evolutionary rate appears to be bimodal. The main peak overlaps with
278 the simulated one and the lower peak cannot be observed in the simulation (Figure
279 1B). The occurrence of the lower peak should be due to strains with the reduced
280 evolutionary rate, representing the effect of repeated spillover events from cold-chains.
281 Therefore, the cold-chain related transmission has a visible effect in the sample.

282

283 **Cold-chain related outbreaks in China**

284 To examine whether cold-chain related transmission happened, we first studied an
285 outbreak in Qingdao, China, that occurred after two dock workers were found to have
286 asymptomatic infections on September 24, 2020 [28]. Two live SARS-CoV-2 particles
287 were isolated from different surface swab samples of frozen cod outer package [21,
288 29], one of which has the identical genomic sequence with the most recent common
289 ancestor (MRCA) of the two strains isolated from the two dock workers (Figure 2A).

290 However, it is significantly unlikely that both workers were infected with the
291 strain^{MRC}A because the probability is very small to accumulate those mutations in two
292 Qingdao strains, respectively, within five days (P -value = 0.039). Thus, two workers
293 may have been infected with different strains, and the isolated strain with C1282T
294 mutation [21] is unlikely due to spot contamination of worker 1. These results are also
295 consistent with that the two workers handled frozen cod packages in different storage
296 cabins [29]. Since the isolated viral sequences have one nucleotide difference, human
297 hosts who caused two cold-chain contaminations should be epidemiologically
298 connected.

299

300 There was an outbreak in Xinfadi, Beijing, China [10, 30] in June 2020.
301 Epidemiologic evidences showed that a booth selling imported salmon might be the
302 origin of infection [10]. We found that the sequences of two isolates
303 (Beijing/IVDC-02-06 and Beijing/BJ0617-01-Y), collected from two Xinfadi cases on
304 June 11 and 14, 2020, are identical to the sequence of an ancestral variant
305 (CGB4268.5142) (Figure 2B) dated March 13, 2020 (95% CI: February 22 –March 14,
306 2020). The descendant of this variant was first isolated from a patient in Taoyuan who
307 recently traveled to European countries [31], and then it was found in Czech Republic,
308 Denmark, India, Colombia, Ecuador, Slovakia, Beijing, and the United States.
309 Moreover, the two Xinfadi strains were found to evolve significantly slowly
310 ($P = 8.28 \times 10^{-4}$ and 6.53×10^{-4} , respectively) after Bonferroni correction [23] for
311 multiple tests (the number of tests is 22) because no mutations were detected between
312 March and June 2020, consistent with the hypothesis of cold-chain related
313 transmission.

314

315 There was an outbreak in Dalian in July 2020 and a multi-city outbreak originated
316 from Yingkou in May 2021 (Supplemental news 1, and 2). The Dalian outbreak
317 started from workers who handled contaminated cold-chain pollock packages from an
318 oversea cargo ship [11]. In the second outbreak, the first case was found in Lu'an.

319 Multiple cases were emerged in multiple cities in the next week and found to have
320 social contacts with confirmed cases in Yingkou (Figure 2C). The two outbreaks seem
321 to be independent because there are no connected cases in nearly 300 days. However,
322 molecular epidemiological evidence on the CGB shows that, the two outbreaks are
323 epidemiologically connected (Figure 2D). Moreover, the result of CGB lineage
324 tracing [20] showed that the sequences of three environmental samples, collected
325 from the pollock package in Dalian in May and June 2020, are identical to that of the
326 MRCA of the cases in the two outbreaks. The Lu'an samples derived only three
327 mutations within 294 days, indicating a severely significantly reduced evolutionary
328 rate ($P = 2.03 \times 10^{-7}$) after Bonferroni correction [23] for multiple tests (the number
329 of tests is 7). The P-value is 4.44×10^{-9} when evolutionary rate heterogeneity is
330 considered. The conclusion remains the same even if using the lower bound of
331 confidence interval of estimated evolutionary rate ($P = 2.93 \times 10^{-5}$). In this case,
332 there are no genomic sequences that are identical with the MRCA of the cases in the
333 two outbreaks, indicating that identical sequences are not always needed to identify
334 mutation-dormant variants. These results suggest that the two outbreaks are
335 epidemiologically connected via a mutation-dormant variant and the Yingkou
336 outbreak is most likely to be cold-chain related.

337

338 Combining all these evidences, it indicates that cold-chain related transmission may
339 cause mutation-dormant variants. It is also consistent with the expectation that the
340 virus re-starts mutating after spillover events from cold-chains. Therefore, cold-chain
341 related transmission could be distinguishable from human-to-human transmission by
342 examining the lineage-specific change of evolutionary rate.

343

344 **Cold-chain related outbreak in Auckland, New Zealand**

345 In August 2020, there was a local outbreak in Auckland after 102 days of no new
346 locally-transmitted Covid-19 cases in New Zealand (Supplemental news 3). The first
347 person who had self-reported illness onset in this outbreak is an employee at a cool

348 storage facility in Auckland. The employee had taken a sick leave since August 3. He,
349 together with other three family members, was tested positive on August 11. The viral
350 lineage of the outbreak is clearly observed in the evolutionary tree (Figure S1). All
351 case-patients carry the mutation T15867G, the Auckland characteristic mutation,
352 together with other eleven mutations. Thus, we searched the whole viral samples to
353 identify strains with exactly the eleven mutations. We found that 120 strains collected
354 from March to August 2020 have the identical genomic sequence (Supplemental
355 Excel file 1). These strains have the eleven mutations and were found in 23 countries
356 (Figure 3A), indicating that the variant did not mutate in this lineage in more than six
357 months. The evolutionary rate is severely significantly reduced ($P = 3.65 \times 10^{-7}$)
358 after Bonferroni correction [23] for multiple tests (the number of tests is 8,437),
359 indicating that the outbreak may be due to a spillover event from cold-chain. The
360 global transmission of the mutation-dormant variant was summarized (Figure 2B),
361 and the origin of the contaminated cold-chain products remains unknown. Moreover,
362 the time of the MRCA of the Auckland strains was inferred to be August 1, 2020,
363 consistent with the known epidemiological information. Thus, it was suggested that
364 the Auckland characteristic mutation T15867G may have occurred in the employee
365 before the virus was transmitted in the local society (Figure 3B).

366

367 **Cold-chain related spread of the earliest SARS-CoV-2 variant**

368 We found that, among the 1,610,125 high-quality genomic sequences, there are 250
369 strains, the genomic sequences of which are identical to Wuhan-Hu-1, the reference
370 genomic sequence (GenBank accession number: NC_045512) [2] (Figure 4A,
371 Supplemental Excel file 1). Wuhan-Hu-1 represents the MRCA sequence of
372 SARS-CoV-2 [20, 32], the earliest SARS-CoV-2 variant. These 250 strains were
373 collected from 32 countries/regions between December 2019 and August 2021. The
374 most (177/250=70.8%) of these non-mutated strains were collected in Asia and North
375 America, but the highest frequency was observed in Africa (Figure S2). In this dataset,
376 the most recent strain was collected in Denmark in August 2021, indicating that the

377 variant did not mutate in the lineage within 20 months. Thus, the variant has an
378 extremely significantly reduced evolutionary rate in the lineage ($P = 7.44 \times 10^{-22}$)
379 after Bonferroni correction [23] for multiple tests (the number of tests is 1,610,125).
380 The conclusion remains the same even if using the lower bound of confidence interval
381 of estimated evolutionary rate ($P = 1.41 \times 10^{-16}$), indicating that our finding is
382 robust with the estimated evolutionary rate of SARS-CoV-2.

383

384 The reduced evolutionary rate is a lineage-specific effect. If the mutation-dormant
385 variant infected a human host (i.e., a spillover event from cold-chain) and was
386 transmitted through social contact, the variant re-started mutating again, similar with
387 ones in the cold-chain related outbreaks in China and New Zealand. Three spillover
388 clades from cold-chains were presented, i.e., the human-to-human transmission
389 lineages identified through genome sampling in Germany (Figure 4A), the United
390 Kingdom (Figure S3A) and the USA (Figure S3B).

391

392 The sequences identical to Wuhan-Hu-1 were found in 32 countries/regions and
393 sequenced by different institutes, so contamination caused by Wuhan-Hu-1 strain
394 samples should not be a probable explanation. Moreover, contamination cannot
395 explain the observed mutations in the genomic sequences after spillover events from
396 cold-chains (Figures 4A, and S3).

397

398 We confirmed our findings using the latest CGB data set (data.2022-02-10,
399 $n = 3,186,359$ genomic sequences) and found multiple recent spillover events in the
400 USA and Denmark (Figure 4B). For example, one spillover event has two descendants
401 (USA/UT-UPHL-211207574214/2021 and USA/UT-UPHL-220103182180/2021),
402 collected at the end of 2021. The two strains carry two and three mutations,
403 respectively, and there is one (C11074CT) in common. The most recent identical
404 strains were found in Denmark and the USA in January 2022, indicating that the
405 variant did not mutate in the lineage within more than two years.

406

407 The persistent appearance of Wuhan-Hu-1 strain across the world increases the
408 possibilities that the Wuhan outbreak is cold-chain related. According to a report from
409 the World Health Organization, the Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market, an epicenter
410 of the Wuhan outbreak, has suppliers of cold-chain products from nearly 20 countries
411 [33]. Considering that the Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market is a market for selling
412 goods to local people, the possibility is relatively low that cold-chain products have
413 been contaminated there and delivered worldwide. Even though there is a suspicion
414 that the wildlife sold in the market were the source of the COVID-19 pandemic [34,
415 35], none of the animal products sampled in the market tested positive [33, 36],
416 indicating that there is no evidence linking the virus to the animal sold in the market.
417 And the multinational spread of the mutation-dormant variant indicating that
418 cold-chain related products may be something like popularly consumed meats, instead
419 of wildlife animals. Overall, the COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan could be associated
420 with spillover events from cold-chains while the origin of contaminated cold-chain
421 products remains to be investigated. The persistent appearance of the
422 mutation-dormant variant indicate that the contaminated products (and the infectivity
423 of virus) have been kept for more than two years, which may provide essential clues
424 for tracing the products and studying the origin of SARS-CoV-2.

425

426 **Cold-chain related spread of D614G variant and Delta VOC**

427 We found the evidence of cold-chain related transmission in the spread of a spike
428 D614G variant. The variant carried D614G mutation in the spike and three mutations
429 in other genomic regions (C3037T, C14408T, and C241T). Interestingly, this variant
430 may have emerged in Europe as early as September of 2019 [37, 38]. This variant has
431 783 identical descendants collected in six continents (49 countries/regions) between
432 February 2020 and May 2021 (Figure 5, Supplemental Excel file 1). The most
433 (675/783=86.2%) of the descendants were found in Europe and North America, but
434 the highest frequency was observed in Africa (Figure S4). Since the variant did not

435 mutate in the lineage in more than one year, its evolutionary rate is extremely
436 significantly reduced in the lineage ($P = 1.54 \times 10^{-17}$) after Bonferroni correction
437 [23] for multiple tests (the number of tests is 1,593,245), suggesting cold-chain
438 related transmission. The results remain significant even if using the lower bound of
439 confidence interval of estimated evolutionary rate ($P = 2.43 \times 10^{-13}$). As expected,
440 this is also a lineage-specific effect. After spillover events from the cold-chain, the
441 mutation-dormant variant re-started mutating normally. Three spillover clades were
442 identified through genome sampling in Germany and other three countries (Figure 5),
443 India (Figure S5A), and the United Kingdom (Figure S5B).

444

445 Recently, the Delta Variant of Concern (VOC), also named as B.1.617.2 lineage,
446 rapidly spread around the world. We searched variants in the Delta VOC which lack
447 mutations in more than 100 days. We identified 15 mutation-dormant variants (Table
448 S2). One variant (CGB531065.591827) appeared on Mar 5, 2021. Within the next five
449 months, it has 34 identical descendant strains and spreads into eight countries without
450 accumulating any new mutations. Another variant (CGB692105.692163) appeared on
451 April 9, 2021, and it has a large number of non-mutated descendants (4,582), the
452 majority of which were found in the United Kingdom (99%, or 4,539/4,582).

453 Moreover, we found three mutation-dormant variants that are linearly connected and
454 separated by one mutation (Figure 6, Supplemental Excel file 1), indicating that
455 patients who caused the recurrent cold-chain contaminations are epidemiologically
456 connected. This is similar with the recurrent cold-chain contaminations resulted in
457 Qingdao outbreak (Figure 2A).

458

459 **The number of mutation-dormant variants and the effects of repeated spillover** 460 **events from cold-chains**

461 We scanned the tremendous SARS-CoV-2 tree with 1,610,125 high-quality genomic
462 sequences to identify the mutation-dormant variants. We found 362 mutation-dormant
463 variants that did not mutate in more than 100 days (Supplemental Excel file 2). By

464 counting their identical descendants, we found 60,796 strains in total. Among these
465 putatively cold-chain related strains, 317 strains were collected from South America,
466 6,053 from Asia, 42,935 from Europe, 244 from Africa, 11,080 from North America,
467 and 167 from Oceania, indicating that cold-chain related transmission may have
468 occurred in all inhabited continents. The percentage of cold-chain related strains is not
469 high among the total samples ($60,796 / 1,610,125 = 3.78\%$) and is similar among
470 different continents (*i.e.*, 2.42%, 4.94%, 4.08%, 3.71%, 2.73%, and 1.62%,
471 respectively).

472

473 **Detection of mutation-dormant variants using millions of genomic sequences**

474 The method used in this study has been implemented in the Coronavirus GenBrowser
475 (CGB) [20]. Thus, newly emerged cold-chain related transmissions could be detected
476 using the CGB. The CGB is provided as a plug-in module for the eGPS software
477 (http://www.egps-software.net/egpscloud/eGPS_Desktop.html) [39]. It not only
478 enables users who have no programming skills to analyze millions of genomic
479 sequences, but also offers an effective surveillance tool for the cold-chain related
480 transmission. An example is shown in the Supplemental Movie.

481

482 **DISCUSSION**

483 In this study we developed a new method to detect cold-chain related SARS-CoV-2
484 transmissions, suitable for the non-epidemic and epidemic areas of COVID-19. We
485 then provided a rough estimate for the frequency of cold-chain related transmission
486 (*i.e.*, spillover events from cold-chains) although it is extremely difficult to be
487 precisely estimated. Due to the random effect of mutation process, the virus may not
488 mutate after a number of human-to-human transmissions, which could make us to
489 over-count the number of cold-chain related transmissions. On the other hand, one
490 viral mutation can occur in the first infected person after a spillover event from
491 cold-chain, such as the observed case in the Auckland outbreak (Figure 3). Those
492 mutated cases were directly linked to cold-chain but not considered when estimating
493 the frequency of cold-chain related transmission. Moreover, our method can detect

494 cold-chain related transmissions only if virus-contaminated products have been frozen
495 for a relatively long period of time before spillover events. If the time duration is short,
496 no mutation-dormant variants can be detected, such as the case in Qingdao outbreak
497 [29] (Figure 2A). Mutation-dormant variants were also sensitive to the search
498 criterion, for example, the mutation-dormant variant that caused the Xinfadi-Beijing
499 outbreak (Figure 2B) was not identified in the section above because it did not mutate
500 in 93 days, less than 100 days. Therefore, considering all these limitations, our results
501 indicate that the frequency of cold-chain related transmission may be in the order of
502 magnitude of 0.1% - 10%.

503

504 To detect mutation-dormant variants, it is important to precisely estimate the
505 genome-wide evolutionary rate of SARS-CoV-2. The estimated evolutionary rate is
506 consistent with the previous analyses [24-26]. It is known that different viral genes
507 have different evolutionary rate [20, 40], thus evolutionary rate heterogeneity has
508 been considered in this study. Moreover, since the effect of cold-chain related
509 transmission may cause an under-estimated evolutionary rate of SARS-CoV-2, the
510 detection of mutation-dormant variants is conservative.

511

512 The identification of mutation-dormant variants was further verified. The
513 mis-submitted collection date could cause a mis-identified mutation-dormant variant
514 (Figure S6), however, this error rate should be low after the CGB quality control [20].
515 It was also required that each mutation-dormant variant has to be associated with at
516 least two non-mutated strains. By removing one of non-mutated strains, the variant
517 remains to be mutation-dormant. Therefore, it is very un-likely that mis-submitted
518 collection date could affect the results. Moreover, the ambiguous nucleotides of a
519 genomic sequence could be mis-imputed in the CGB [20]. Although this probability is
520 small, it is required that each mutation-dormant variant must be determined by at least
521 two sequences without any ambiguous nucleotides on the positions that do not define
522 the mutation-dormant variant. Since the CGB [20] analyzes the sequence

523 corresponding to the reference sequence between nucleotides 100 and 29,800 of each
524 genome, unseen mutations can happen in two sides of genome. To verify this issue,
525 we examined the corresponding alignments of mutation-dormant variants and found
526 that our conclusion remains unchanged (Supplemental Excel file 1). Therefore, all
527 these confounding factors have been considered in this study to ensure the reliability
528 of the identified mutation-dormant variants.

529

530 We then examined other alternative hypotheses that may cause the mutation-dormant
531 variants. Poor sequencing quality may result in this observation, however, the
532 percentage of ambiguous nucleotides is very small (less than 0.069%) after the quality
533 control of CGB [20]. Moreover, we require that, to identify a single mutation-dormant
534 variant, there must be certain number of genomic sequences with no ambiguous
535 nucleotides, and repeated spillover events must be identified by multiple independent
536 institutes. Those events have usually been observed across different nations or even
537 continents. Thus, the poor sequencing quality is very unlikely to explain our
538 observations.

539

540 It could be argued that purifying selection may lead to a mutation-dormant variant [20,
541 40]. However, the effect of purifying selection has been considered in the analysis and
542 it cannot explain the fast accumulated mutations occurred after spillover events from
543 cold-chains. Moreover, there are plenty of studies [41-44] to elucidate the within-host
544 diversity of SARS-CoV-2. Within-host variants are present in most SARS-CoV-2
545 samples while the diversity level is low. In other words, most samples harbored few
546 within-host variants and very few within-host variants were detected in more than two
547 patients. Importantly, within-host diversity can be rapidly lost in a few generations
548 [44]. Therefore, within-host diversity does not affect our conclusions. Also,
549 recombination could occur between strains [45], however, it does not alter the
550 evolutionary rate. Thus, recombination does not affect our conclusions. Overall, after
551 considering these alternative hypotheses, spillover events from cold-chains should be

552 the only explanation for our observations. When there is no epidemiological
553 information for cold-chain related transmission, mutation-dormant variants may be
554 good candidates for investigating how cold-chain related transmission occurred.

555

556 If an evolutionary tree is constructed by traditional methods [46-49], it will be
557 difficult to reveal the cold-chain related transmission (Figures 3, 4, 5 and 6). All those
558 cold-chain related strains will be clustered together since those strains are extremely
559 similar. Therefore, it is recommended that the internal nodes of the tip-dated tree
560 should be dated using an effective maximum-likelihood method (TreeTime) [20, 50].
561 Moreover, our results demonstrate that it is important to have a panoramic vision of
562 the transmission and evolution of SARS-CoV-2 [20], by properly analyzing all the
563 high-quality SARS-CoV-2 genomic sequences and their associated meta-data.

564

565 The cold-chain related transmission may have happened globally but is very rare, thus
566 it makes human societies relatively easier to control the transmission. Moreover, the
567 proper protection and training for workers of cold-chain facilities should be important.
568 It can not only protect workers against cold-chain related infection, but also prevent
569 potential contaminations from workers who are unfortunately infected. It would also
570 be helpful to educate consumers how to properly handle cold-chain products produced
571 from the epidemic areas of COVID-19. Overall, the well-established cold-chain is
572 extremely essential for the economy and the global distribution of foods and drinks.
573 Therefore, the prevention of cold-chain related transmission is highly necessary to
574 reduce the impact of the pandemic on the global cold-chain and avoid the cold-chain
575 associated adaptation of SARS-CoV-2 in the future.

576

577 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST**

578 Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

579

580

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590

591 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

592 Conceptualization, D.Y., J.Z., J.Y., Y.H.P.; G.P.Z., Y.P.Z, W.Z., G.Z., H.L.; Coding and
593 software development: D.Y., J.Y., H.M., Z.Q.H., L.D.; Data integration, D.Y., J.Z.,
594 J.Y., R.C., B.T., G.D.; Data analysis, D.Y., J.Z., J.Y., Y.H.P.; Writing, D.Y., J.Y., Y.H.P.,
595 G.P.Z., Y.P.Z, W.Z., G.Z., H.L.; Supervision & funding acquisition, Y.H.P., G.P.Z.,
596 Y.P.Z, W.Z., G.Z., H.L.

597

598 **DATA AND SOFTWARE AVAILABILITY**

599 The data was downloaded from <https://ngdc.cncb.ac.cn/ncov/apis/>, and the CGB is
600 freely available from http://www.egps-software.net/egpscloud/eGPS_Desktop.html, as
601 a plug-in of the eGPS Desktop [39]. The algorithm developed in this study was
602 integrated into the CGB, to search for mutation-dormant variants. It is available in the
603 version 1.13, or the latest version of the eGPS Desktop.

604

605

606 **REFERENCES**

- 607 [1] Zhu N, Zhang D, Wang W, et al. A novel coronavirus from patients with pneumonia in China,
608 2019. *N Engl J Med*, 2020, 382: 727-733
- 609 [2] Wu F, Zhao S, Yu B, et al. A new coronavirus associated with human respiratory disease in China.
610 *Nature*, 2020, 579: 265-269
- 611 [3] Lu R, Zhao X, Li J, et al. Genomic characterisation and epidemiology of 2019 novel coronavirus:
612 implications for virus origins and receptor binding. *Lancet*, 2020, 395: 565-574
- 613 [4] Wang CC, Prather KA, Sznitman J, et al. Airborne transmission of respiratory viruses. *Science*,
614 2021, 373: eabd9149
- 615 [5] Liu Y, Ning Z, Chen Y, et al. Aerodynamic analysis of SARS-CoV-2 in two Wuhan hospitals.
616 *Nature*, 2020, 582: 557-560
- 617 [6] Chin AWH, Chu JTS, Perera MRA, et al. Stability of SARS-CoV-2 in different environmental
618 conditions. *Lancet Microbe*, 2020, 1: e10-e10, [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2666-5247\(20\)30003-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2666-5247(20)30003-3)
- 619 [7] Lewis D. COVID-19 rarely infects through surfaces. So why are we still deep cleaning? *Nature*,
620 2021, 590: 26-28
- 621 [8] Wu Z, Jin Q, Wu G, et al. SARS-CoV-2's origin should be investigated worldwide for pandemic
622 prevention. *Lancet*, 2021,
- 623 [9] Mallapaty S, Maxmen A, Callaway E. Mysteries persist after World Health Organization reports on
624 COVID-origin search. *Nature*, 2021, 590: 371-372
- 625 [10] Pang X, Ren L, Wu S, et al. Cold-chain food contamination as the possible origin of Covid-19
626 resurgence in Beijing. *Natl Sci Rev*, 2020, 7: 1861-1864
- 627 [11] Ma H, Zhang J, Wang J, et al. COVID-19 outbreak caused by contaminated packaging of imported
628 cold-chain products — Liaoning Province, China, July 2020. *China CDC Weekly*, 2021, 3:
629 441-447, <https://doi.org/10.46234/ccdcw2021.114>
- 630 [12] Han SL, Liu XW. Can imported cold food cause COVID-19 recurrent outbreaks? A review.
631 *Environ Chem Lett*, 2022, 20: 119-129, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10311-021-01312-w>
- 632 [13] Sobolik JS, Sajewski ET, Jaykus LA, et al. Low risk of SARS-CoV-2 transmission via fomite, even
633 in cold-chain. *medRxiv*, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.23.21262477>
- 634 [14] Riddell S, Goldie S, Hill A, et al. The effect of temperature on persistence of SARS-CoV-2 on
635 common surfaces. *Virol J*, 2020, 17: 145
- 636 [15] Elbe S, Buckland-Merrett G. Data, disease and diplomacy: GISAID's innovative contribution to
637 global health. *Glob Chall*, 2017, 1: 33-46
- 638 [16] Shu YL, McCauley J. GISAID: Global initiative on sharing all influenza data - from vision to
639 reality. *Eurosurveillance*, 2017, 22: 2-4
- 640 [17] Sayers EW, Beck J, Bolton EE, et al. Database resources of the National Center for Biotechnology
641 Information. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 2021, 49: D10-D17
- 642 [18] Xue YB, Bao YM, Zhang Z, et al. Database resources of the National Genomics Data Center,
643 China National Center for Bioinformatics in 2021. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 2021, 49: D18-D28,
644 <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa1022>
- 645 [19] Gong Z, Zhu J-W, Li C-P, et al. An online coronavirus analysis platform from the National
646 Genomics Data Center. *Zool Res*, 2020, 41: 705-708,
647 <https://dx.doi.org/10.24272/j.issn.2095-8137.2020.065>
- 648 [20] Yu D, Yang X, Tang B, et al. Coronavirus GenBrowser for monitoring the transmission and
649 evolution of SARS-CoV-2. *Brief Bioinform*, 2022, bbab583, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbab583>

- 650 [21] Liu P, Yang M, Zhao X, et al. Cold-chain transportation in the frozen food industry may have
651 caused a recurrence of COVID-19 cases in destination: Successful isolation of SARS-CoV-2 virus
652 from the imported frozen cod package surface. *Biosafety and Health*, 2020, 2: 199-201,
653 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bsheal.2020.11.003>
- 654 [22] Wang Y, Dai G, Gu Z, et al. Accelerated evolution of an *Lhx2* enhancer shapes mammalian social
655 hierarchies. *Cell Res*, 2020, 30: 408-420, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41422-020-0308-7>
- 656 [23] Dunn OJ. Multiple comparisons among means. *J Am Stat Assoc*, 1961, 56: 52-64
- 657 [24] Nie Q, Li X, Chen W, et al. Phylogenetic and phylodynamic analyses of SARS-CoV-2. *Virus Res*,
658 2020, 287: 198098
- 659 [25] van Dorp L, Richard D, Tan CCS, et al. No evidence for increased transmissibility from recurrent
660 mutations in SARS-CoV-2. *Nat Commun*, 2020, 11: 5986
- 661 [26] Duchene S, Featherstone L, Haritopoulou-Sinanidou M, et al. Temporal signal and the
662 phylodynamic threshold of SARS-CoV-2. *Virus Evol*, 2020, 6: veaa061
- 663 [27] Yu W-B, Tang G-D, Zhang L, et al. Decoding the evolution and transmissions of the novel
664 pneumonia coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2 / HCoV-19) using whole genomic data. *Zoological research*,
665 2020, 41: 247-257, <http://dx.doi.org/10.24272/j.issn.2095-8137.2020.022>
- 666 [28] Xing Y, Wong GWK, Ni W, et al. Rapid response to an outbreak in Qingdao, China. *N Engl J Med*,
667 2020, 383: e129, <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmc2032361>
- 668 [29] Ma H, Wang Z, Zhao X, et al. Long distance transmission of SARS-CoV-2 from contaminated cold
669 chain products to humans — Qingdao City, Shandong Province, China, september 2020. *China*
670 *CDC Weekly*, 2021, 3: 637-644, <https://doi.org/10.46234/ccdcw2021.164>
- 671 [30] Zhang Y, Pan Y, Zhao X, et al. Genomic characterization of SARS-CoV-2 identified in a
672 reemerging COVID-19 outbreak in Beijing's Xinfadi market in 2020. *Biosaf Health*, 2020, 2:
673 202-205, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bsheal.2020.08.006>
- 674 [31] Gong YN, Tsao KC, Hsiao MJ, et al. SARS-CoV-2 genomic surveillance in Taiwan revealed novel
675 ORF8-deletion mutant and clade possibly associated with infections in Middle East. *Emerg*
676 *Microbes Infect*, 2020, 9: 1457-1466, <https://doi.org/10.1080/22221751.2020.1782271>
- 677 [32] Bedford T, Greninger AL, Roychoudhury P, et al. Cryptic transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in
678 Washington state. *Science*, 2020, 370: 571-575
- 679 [33] WHO-convened Global Study of Origins of SARS-CoV-2: China Part, 2021,
680 <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/who-convened-global-study-of-origins-of-sars-cov-2-chin>
681 [a-part](https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/who-convened-global-study-of-origins-of-sars-cov-2-chin)
- 682 [34] Lytras S, Xia W, Hughes J, et al. The animal origin of SARS-CoV-2. *Science*, 2021, 373: 968-970,
683 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abh0117>
- 684 [35] Worobey M, Levy JI, Malpica Serrano LM, et al. The Huanan market was the epicenter of
685 SARS-CoV-2 emergence. *Zenodo*, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6299600>
- 686 [36] Liu WJ, Liu P, Lei W, et al. Surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 in the environment and animal samples
687 of the Huanan Seafood Market. *Research Square*, 2022,
688 <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1370392/v1>
- 689 [37] Amendola A, Canuti M, Bianchi S, et al. Molecular evidence for SARS-CoV-2 in samples
690 collected from patients with morbilliform eruptions since late summer 2019 in Lombardy,
691 Northern Italy. *SSRN*, 2021, <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3883274>
- 692 [38] Ruan Y, Wen H, Hou M, et al. The twin-beginnings of COVID-19 in Asia and Europe – One
693 prevails quickly. *Natl Sci Rev*, 2022,

694 [39] Yu D, Dong L, Yan F, et al. eGPS 1.0: comprehensive software for multi-omic and evolutionary
695 analyses. *Natl Sci Rev*, 2019, 6: 867-869, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwz079>
696 [40] Tang X, Wu C, Li X, et al. On the origin and continuing evolution of SARS-CoV-2. *Natl Sci Rev*,
697 2020, 7: 1012-1023
698 [41] Lythgoe KA, Hall M, Ferretti L, et al. SARS-CoV-2 within-host diversity and transmission.
699 *Science*, 2021, 372:
700 [42] San JE, Ngcapu S, Kanzi AM, et al. Transmission dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 within-host diversity
701 in two major hospital outbreaks in South Africa. *Virus Evol*, 2021, 7: veab041
702 [43] Al Khatib HA, Benslimane FM, Elbashir IE, et al. Within-host diversity of SARS-CoV-2 in
703 COVID-19 patients with variable disease severities. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*, 2020, 10:
704 575-613
705 [44] Lauring AS. Within-host viral diversity: a window into viral evolution. *Annual review of virology*,
706 2020, 7: 63-81
707 [45] Jackson B, Boni MF, Bull MJ, et al. Generation and transmission of interlineage recombinants in
708 the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. *Cell*, 2021, 184: 5179-5188
709 [46] Saitou N, Nei M. The neighbor-joining method: a new method for reconstructing phylogenetic
710 trees. *Mol Biol Evol*, 1987, 4: 406-425
711 [47] Hartigan JA. Minimum mutation fits to a given tree. *Biometrics*, 1973, 29: 53-65
712 [48] Kozlov AM, Darriba D, Flouri T, et al. RAxML-NG: a fast, scalable and user-friendly tool for
713 maximum likelihood phylogenetic inference. *Bioinformatics*, 2019, 35: 4453-4455
714 [49] Rannala B, Yang Z. Probability distribution of molecular evolutionary trees: A new method of
715 phylogenetic inference. *J Mol Evol*, 1996, 43: 304-311
716 [50] Sagulenko P, Puller V, Neher RA. TreeTime: Maximum-likelihood phylodynamic analysis. *Virus*
717 *Evol*, 2018, 4: vex042
718
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720
 721 **Figure 1. Comparison between human-to-human transmission and cold-chain**
 722 **related transmission.**

723 A) Illustration of SARS-CoV-2 transmission tree under two circumstances. The
 724 light-yellow background represents human-to-human transmission and the
 725 light-blue background represents cold-chain related transmission. Each notch of
 726 the branches represents a mutation. Contamination is indicated by a transmission
 727 from an infected human host to a cold-chain. Blue human icon represents human
 728 infected due to a spillover event from cold chain, and orange human icon
 729 represents human infected by virus from another human. Two spillover clades
 730 from cold-chain were shown, indicated as the orange empty circles, and 12
 731 spillover singletons were presented, two of which were marked by the red arrows,
 732 as examples.

733 B) The observed and simulated distribution of evolutionary rate among different
 734 SARS-CoV-2 strains.

735

736

737 **Figure 2. Cold-chain related outbreaks in China.**

738 A) View of lineages associated with Qingdao outbreak. Qingdao/IVDC-01-10 and

739 Qingdao/IVDC-02-10 are the two SARS-CoV-2 strains collected on September 24,

740 2020 from two dock workers in Qingdao, China. Two cold-chain related

741 transmissions are indicated. Each notch of the branches represents a mutation.

742 Mutations of the Qingdao strains are indicated. The CGB ID of the subtree root is
743 CGB81543.719049.

744 B) View of lineages associated with Beijing outbreak. The ancestral viral strain found
745 in early March 2020 is marked with a dark-red solid circle and an arrowhead. This
746 strain is identical to the two strains (Beijing/IVDC-02-06 and
747 Beijing/BJ0617-01-Y) collected from two Xinfadi cases on June 11 and 14, 2020.
748 Each notch of the branches represents a mutation. The branches with no mutations
749 are highlighted. The CGB ID of the subtree root is CGB4268.5142, and the
750 number of strains is 22.

751 C) Schematic diagram of Dalian and Yingkou outbreaks in 10 months.

752 D) View of the lineage associated with Dalian and Yingkou (as Lu'an samples)
753 outbreaks. The node marked with a blue solid circle has the same genomic
754 sequence with the environmental samples collected from the pollock package of
755 the ship "DK" during May 30 – June 4, 2020[11] (GISAID accession numbers:
756 EPI_ISL_2170892 – EPI_ISL_2170894). Each notch of the branches represents a
757 mutation. The CGB ID of the subtree root is CGB32671.884167, and the number
758 of strains is 16.

759

760
761
762 **Figure 3. Cold-chain related outbreak in Auckland, New Zealand.**

763 A) The genomic sequences of 120 strains of the evolutionary tree are identical with
764 that of an ancestral variant (CGB509.2692), indicated as a blue solid circle at the
765 root of the subtree. The variant carries eleven mutations (C241T, C3037T, C4002T,
766 G10097A, C13536T, C14408T, A23403G, C23731T, G28881A, G28882A, and
767 G28883C). The spillover event from cold-chain is indicated by a thermometer
768 icon. Moreover, the Auckland clade is derived, as indicated by a four prism. A
769 detailed view of the Auckland clade is shown in the sub-panel ($n = 56$). The

770 characteristic mutation of Auckland outbreak (T15867G) is marked with a red
771 triangle in the clade. Each notch of the branches represents a mutation. Illness
772 transmission through social contacts in the Auckland outbreak is indicated by four
773 linked people icons in the sub-panel.

774 B) Schematic diagram of the Auckland outbreak. The origin of cold-chain related
775 infection source remains unknown. The ancestral variant (CGB509.2692),
776 carrying eleven mutations, had spread to multiple continents during March to
777 August 2020. The contaminated goods infected the patient zero (in blue) in
778 Auckland in Aug 2020. The virus in the patient mutated once (T15867G) before
779 being transmitted to other human hosts.

780

781
782 **Figure 4. Cold-chain related spread of the earliest SARS-CoV-2 variant.**

783 A) Tree visualization of 250 strains non-mutated between November 24, 2019 and
784 August 2, 2021. These strains have the same state as the root (*i.e.*, the reference
785 genome sequence NC_045512) [2]. The main tree has experienced sample
786 filtering and only the strains with the identical genomic sequences were shown.
787 The mutation-dormant variant (CGB1.3) is indicated as a blue solid circle at the
788 root of the subtree. The cold-chain related transmission is indicated by a
789 thermometer icon. Moreover, a cold-chain related transmission lineage through
790 social contacts is indicated by a four prism. The spillover clade from cold-chain is

791 shown in the sub-panel. The CGB ID of the clade is CGB440761.572094. Each
792 notch of branches represents a mutation. Illness transmission through social
793 contacts is indicated by four linked people icons. Blue human icon represents
794 human infected due to the spillover event from cold chain, and orange human icon
795 represents human infected by virus from another human. The light-yellow
796 background represents human-to-human transmission.

797 **B)** Tree visualization of recent spillover events related to the earliest SARS-CoV-2
798 variant after June, 2021. The latest CGB data set was used (data.2022-02-10,
799 $n = 3,186,359$ genomic sequences). Since there are only a few strains, the tree
800 was not filtered to show only identical genomic sequences. Three independent
801 virus strain transmission clusters were highlighted, indicating three spillover
802 events from cold-chain. Since multiple mutations occurred in the clusters, it may
803 indicate multiple local transmission events after the spillover events.

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809 **Figure 5. The mutation-dormant D614G variant and cold-chain related**
 810 **transmission lineages detected through genome sampling.**

811 Tree visualization of 783 strains non-mutated between January 2, 2020 and May 7,
 812 2021. These strains are the descendants of a variant with four mutations (C3037T,
 813 A23403G, C14408T, and C241T) emerged before December 24, 2019. The
 814 non-synonymous mutation A23403G is known as S:D614G. The CGB ID of the tree
 815 root is CGB35.120. A clade derived from a cold-chain related spillover event is shown
 816 in the sub-panel. The CGB ID of the clade is CGB236904.257621. Blue human icon
 817 represents human infected due to the spillover event from cold chain, and orange
 818 human icon represents human infected by virus from another human. The light-yellow
 819 background represents human-to-human transmission.

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823 **Figure 6. Three mutation-dormant Delta VOCs and cold-chain related UK**
 824 **transmission lineages detected through genome sampling.**

825 Three mutation-dormant variants are indicated as three blue solid circles near the root
 826 of the subtree (CGB531065.580055). Three characteristic mutations are marked to
 827 distinguish three variants. A clade derived from a cold-chain related spillover event is
 828 indicated by a thermometer icon. Three spillover clades are presented in the
 829 sub-panels. Their characteristic mutations are labeled, and the CGB IDs of colored
 830 four prisms are CGB1352928.1377873, CGB1224042.1265384, and
 831 CGB1488858.1503350, respectively. Blue human icon represents human infected due
 832 to the spillover event from cold chain, and orange human icon represents human
 833 infected by virus from another human. The light-yellow background represents
 834 human-to-human transmission.

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